

PROJECT DELIVERABLE REPORT

Greening the economy in line with
the sustainable development goals

D7.3.2 NAI ADES Front-End and HMI Mechanisms and Integrated Decision Support Engine – User manual for Carouge

A holistic water ecosystem for digitisation of urban water sector

SC5-11-2018

Digital solutions for water: linking the physical and digital world for water solutions

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Abbreviations

ACF	Autocorrelation Function
HMI	Human Machine Interface
IP	Internet Protocol
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
NN	Neural Network
OECD	Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development
UC	Use Case

1. Summary

This report provides the user manual for UC Carouge, in order to be translated to French for the convenience of the end-users, as well as the smooth adaptation of HMI to the Use Case.

The initial report was delivered in English and it was based on D7.3 HMI and integrated Decision Support System.

The final report was translated in French by the UC leaders, in order to be delivered to the end-users.

2. Log In & Language

The steps for the end-user to log in is the following:

- Connect to <http://167.71.44.124:2030/>

*This IP will change in future and it will be replaced with the final NAIADES domain name.

Figure 2-1 Connect to Keyrock

The final Carouge end-users are varied to:

- Watering Operator, this user sees only the watering screen
- Carouge Manager, this user sees all the UC screens
- Fountain Manager, this user sees only the fountains

Their credentials (passwords) will be delivered confidentially and not in this document.

- Log in as e.g., Carouge Manager

The end-user clicks on “connect to Keyrock” button (see the previous figure) and he is redirected to Keyrock.

 A screenshot of the Keyrock Identity Manager login page. The header shows the 'keyrock Identity Manager' logo. The main content area is split into two panels. The left panel displays the 'Naiades-KT' logo and the text 'Carouge-Braila-Alicante'. The right panel is titled 'Sign In' and contains a form with fields for 'Email' (containing 'carouge-manager@test.com') and 'Password' (masked with dots). Below the password field is a 'remember me' checkbox. A 'Sign In' button is located at the bottom right of the form. At the bottom of the form, there are links for 'Sign up', 'Forgot password', and 'Confirmation not recieved?'.

Figure 2-2 Log in to Keyrock

- The end-user gives their credentials and click on the “Sign In” button. Then, they can see the HMI screen.

Figure 2-3 HMI Screen

Finally, the end-user can navigate to HMI screens. Before this, there is the capability to select the preferred language (English or French).

- Select Language

The end-user click on the drop-down on the top-right menu. He can leave the predefined language, which is English as it is shown in the figure bellow.

Figure 2-4 English Language option

Or he/she can select French, by clicking “FR” in the drop-down.

Figure 2-5 Figure 2 4 French Language option

After this, the end-user can navigate to the HMI to the language of his convenience.

3. Watering

This screen is provided by the ICCS partners.

In the main view page (Figure below), users can see all boxes on a map represented by a marker, the colour of which indicates their watering needs.

Figure 3-1 Main view page of Flower Boxes.

Also, city workers can see all boxes in a list that is sorted by the suggested date of watering and check the watering status. Boxes that according to the recommendation of the NAIADES AI module should be watered today are listed on the top, followed by those that need to be watered tomorrow and the day after.

Figure 3-2 Boxes list

In addition to the information about when the boxes of a cluster should be watered (today, tomorrow, day after tomorrow), the employees can also see the humidity level and the suggested amount of water for each box.

Figure 3-3 Box Information (humidity, etc.)

The boxes that need to be watered today are annotated with red colour, while the boxes that need to be watered tomorrow and later than tomorrow are annotated with a green colour. The user can edit each box and view more details by clicking on the box name.

City workers can filter the boxes of the list by the suggested watering day (today, tomorrow or after tomorrow).

Figure 3-4 Filter the boxes

In the example shown in Figure below the user has applied the filter so that s/he can see only the boxes that need to be watered today.

Figure 3-5 List view page showing the boxes that need water today.

When the user clicks on a specific box, a pop-up window appears showing its details (Figure below), including the date it was watered last, the suggested date it should be watered next, the type of the flowers it contains and its sun exposure. Through the pop-up the user can navigate to the box details or problem reporting pages.

Figure 3-6 Main view page showing the box details pop up window

- Problem Reporting

City workers can also report problems per flower box by clicking on the “Report new issue” button.

Figure 3-7 Report new issue

The application redirects them on the page depicted in Figure below where different types of problems related to watering can be reported, including broken sensors, wrong data, problems with the box, flowers destroyed etc. User can select the type of the reported problem and add a description related to the reported issue. After entering the issue type and the description, the user clicks on the “Report” button. A new issue is created and the app redirects the user to the main view presented.

Figure 3-8 Report problem page.

Users can also see all the reported issues for each box by clicking on the “Issues” button. Figure below depicts an indicative example of all the reported issues for Box 1.

Figure 3-9 Screenshot of page showing the reported issues of Box #1.

- Box Details View

In the “Box Details” view users can see historical humidity measurements, watering recommendation data and past watering logs, for the particular box (Figure below). At the final version of the app the graphs showing soil electroconductivity, soil temperature and battery level were added. Also, the graph presenting the soil water requirements history was updated to show data for both old and Dragino sensors. Finally,

the watering predictions graph was updated to show comparisons of the actual and predicted watering amount per day.

Figure 3-10 "Box Details – History" page

- PDF report

Furthermore, users can download as a pdf file a monthly report of the water consumption per box. Figure below shows an example of such a report.

Figure 3-11 Water Consumption Report of Box #4.

- Cluster Details

The NAIADES Watering app tracks the position of the truck and when it senses that the truck is near the cluster, the app automatically opens a “Cluster Details” dashboard. On the Cluster Details page (Figure below), city workers can see the predicted amount of water that each box and each the cluster needs.

There is a prediction provided by the AI module for the box that has the sensor and is already stored in the Context broker. Based on this prediction, average values for the total water required for the Cluster and the boxes could be inferred.

Each time the employee closes the hose, an event is sent from the truck sensor with the TruckId, WaterUsed and GPS Location. The information is sent through MQTT. The Context Broker listens to this information and stores it. The NAIADES app listens to this information and uses it to update the information shown in the dashboard. The Cluster Details page is updated based on the watering sensor values, and the employee views the amount of water that he has used and if this is in the recommended range.

Figure 3-12 Cluster Details page.

On the Cluster Details page, city workers can also provide feedback regarding the watering needs of each cluster. A city worker can click either the button “Dry plants” or the button “No watering required” at the cluster details page of the watering app to send feedback to watering dashboard administrators.

Figure 3-13 Feedback buttons regarding the watering needs

Moreover, they can click the button “Report new issue” in order to provide feedback. The app redirects them to the “Report problem” page.

Figure 3-14 Report new issue

- Reports

Managers and city workers can see monthly and daily reports of the water consumption per box and per cluster by clicking on the “Reports” button at the main page of the watering app (Figure below).

Figure 3-15 Main view page showing the Report options.

Users can see a compiled monthly report of the water consumption per box and per cluster (Figure below). They can see the trend of water consumption per cluster, the time spent and the predicted watering amount and have a monitoring of the monthly progress.

Also, they can see the number of km by trucks, as well as a review of the reported problems per cluster. Users can also adjust the timeframe of the periodic report by selecting different time ranges using the datepicker.

Figure 3-16 Water Consumption Monthly Report.

Furthermore, users can download as a pdf file a monthly report of the water consumption per box and per cluster. Figure below shows an example of such a report.

Figure 3-17 Water Consumption Monthly Report as PDF

City workers can also see and download daily reports (Figure below). When they return to the office, they could see the information of the day. Daily report presents the total water consumption and watering time of the day. It also shows the quantity of water used per box, the time of watering, the humidity level and the next watering amount per box. In addition, it compares the last watering session with the previous session per box.

Figure 3-18 Water Consumption Daily Report

Furthermore, users can download as a pdf file the daily report of the water consumption per box. Figure below shows an example of such a report.

Today's Report

Overall

Todays Water Consumption
30 lt

Todays Watering Time
2 hrs

Watered Today

Box ID	Humidity Level	Amount of watering	Time of watering	Next watering amount	Amount of previous watering
--------	----------------	--------------------	------------------	----------------------	-----------------------------

Figure 3-19 Water Consumption Daily Report as PDF

- Route

Clicking on the button “View suggested route for visiting boxes” from the main view page, the user is navigated to the Route view depicted in the Figure below. The app calls the Google directions’ API to calculate the fastest route from the current location of the user to the location where the trucks are parked at the end of their shift, by including as waypoints the list of coordinates of boxes that still need to be watered today. In this view, users can also see the next cluster of flower boxes that needs to be watered together with the amount of water the box needs. The operator is free to ignore the advice about which cluster should be watered next, in which case a new route can be calculated. When the truck is moving between the location of the clusters, the user’s position is updated on the map. Also, city worker can see all boxes in a list that is sorted by the worker’s location and check the watering status. The list view is dynamically adjusted to show nearby clusters on top, based on the employee’s location. Finally, users can apply a filter, so that they can select for which day they want to see the suggested route.

Figure 3-20 “View route” page showing suggested route for today.

- Multilingual Support

Finally, it should be noted that the application has multilingual support, with content provided in both English and French. The translation in French was performed in collaboration with the partners from Carouge as public employees there mainly speak French. Figure 42 shows for example the main view page in French.

Figure 3-21 Indicative view of the watering app in French.

4. Fountains

This screen is provided by KT.

The end-user can navigate to the fountains and the swimming pool from Carouge.

Figure 4-1 Fountain Screen 1

Figure 4-2 Fountains Screen 2

In the Fountains screen, HMI provides the UI of a fountain and a swimming pool in Carouge area. This screen aims of helping the end-user to have a complete awareness on:

- Report form: When the user presses the New Report button, he is able to fill a Daily Report form

- Water Quality measurements,
- Water Quality Predictions/Forecast
- Weather Prediction

On a daily and next day’s basis.

Furthermore, the above inputs feed DSS with valid data and as an outcome, the end-user is able to see alerts e.g., on Chlorine, Chlorate levels.

As a result, the end-user is enhanced with situation awareness, in order to take action if need for both the fountain and the Swimming Pool in Carouge.

- Water Quality

The end-user can see real-time measurements for pH level, free chlorine, total chlorine, chlorate level, temperature, turbidity and redox. This is visible in the blue column on the left.

	Real Time (Thu 06/10/2022 14:19)	+6h (Tue 25/10/2022 11:45)	+12h (Tue 25/10/2022 17:45)	+18h (Tue 25/10/2022 23:45)	+24h (Wed 26/10/2022 05:45)	+30h (Wed 26/10/2022 11:45)	+36h (Wed 26/10/2022 17:45)	+42h (Wed 26/10/2022 23:45)	+48h (Thu 27/10/2022 05:45)	Hourly average	Daily average
pH	7.73	7.62↓	7.66↓	7.59↓	7.68↓	7.68↓	7.71↓	7.71↓	7.59↓	7.73	7.73
Free Chlorine (mg/L)	0.18	0.20↑	0.21↑	0.21↑	0.21↑	0.21↑	0.20↑	0.20↑	0.20↑	0.18	0.18
Total Chlorine (mg/L)	0.37	1.57↑	1.46↑	1.12↑	0.72↑	1.41↑	1.77↑	1.10↑	1.73↑	0.37	0.37
Chlorate (mg/L)	1.95	1.79↓	1.67↓	1.38↓	1.34↓	1.29↓	1.37↓	1.26↓	1.14↓	1.95	1.95
Temperature (°C)	17.2	22.48↑	21.63↑	20.45↑	20.97↑	21.07↑	21.89↑	21.41↑	21.40↑	17.20	17.20
Turbidity (NTU)	2.4	0.00↓	0.00↓	0.00↓	0.00↓	0.00↓	0.00↓	0.00↓	0.00↓	2.40	2.40
Redox (V)	0.354	0.57↑	0.60↑	0.57↑	0.58↑	0.59↑	0.60↑	0.64↑	0.64↑	0.35	0.35

Figure 4-3 Water Quality

This functionality only retrieves the above data from the last detected datetime. If the data are outdated, a notification message will be shown on the top of the screen, as in the above figure.

In the next columns, the end-user can see the predicted values for the next hours and 3 days of the aforementioned measurements. Arrows are also provided, in order to aware the user for the behaviour of the predicted measurements (e.g., red if the measurements are lower than the real-time value, green in if it is higher).

There is also the option to click on the “Graph” button on the top-right of the figure, in order to see a graph with the historical data and the water quality prediction.

Figure 4-4 Historical Data and Predictions

The above graph visualizes the incoming value for each of the water quality measurements (pH, chlorine, etc.) and combines its prediction to a more interactive dashboard. The predictions are analyzed in the following chapter.

If the end-user hovers on the line, a [pop-up](#) will appear with the detailed values.

The above forecast is coming from the “[Local Station](#)” of Carouge. There is also the option to select from the drop-down (it is shown in the above figure) the predictions from the “[Environmental](#)” Station.

The data from the different stations are coming from calls to different entities.

- Select Local or Environmental Station

Figure 4-5 Selection of Station

The end-user has to click the drop-down under the datetime and choose the preferable station.

- [Weather Forecast](#)

The Weather Forecast is the following table. This component provides information about [temperature](#), [relative humidity](#) and [wind speed](#) for the next 3 days in the Carouge area.

Weather													
	Real Time (Thu 17/11/2022 23:01)	Predictions +6h (Thu 17/11/2022 20:00)	+12h (Fri 18/11/2022 02:00)	+18h (Fri 18/11/2022 08:00)	+24h (Fri 18/11/2022 14:00)	+30h (Fri 18/11/2022 20:00)	+36h (Sat 19/11/2022 02:00)	+42h (Sat 19/11/2022 08:00)	+48h (Sat 19/11/2022 14:00)	+54h (Sat 19/11/2022 20:00)	+60h (Sun 20/11/2022 02:00)	+66h (Sun 20/11/2022 08:00)	+72h (Sun 20/11/2022 14:00)
Temperature (°C)	11.8	8.9 ↓	10.2 ↓	14.2 ↑	14.8 ↑	9.9 ↓	7.6 ↓	10.1 ↓	11.4 ↓	13.7 ↑	12.9 ↑	16.3 ↑	16.8 ↑
Relative Humidity (%)	84.4	94.8 ↑	92.3 ↑	67.0 ↓	59.2 ↓	81.5 ↓	89.5 ↑	84.7 ↑	77.1 ↓	69.5 ↓	73.9 ↓	57.5 ↓	53.7 ↓
Wind Speed (km/h)	0.136	-0.0 ↓	0.5 ↑	1.1 ↑	0.8 ↑	0.7 ↑	0.4 ↑	0.5 ↑	0.4 ↑	1.3 ↑	0.9 ↑	1.8 ↑	1.7 ↑

Figure 4-6 Weather Forecast in Carouge

Again, the end-user has the capability of viewing the weather prediction either from the local nor the environmental stations.

- DSS Feed

Under the weather prediction, the end-user can see DSS alerts. These are warnings created when the measurements of the water quality are close to the lowest permissible level.

DSS Feed

17/11/2022 22:06
Alert: pH value is higher than normal (7)!
 Action:
 Add chloridic acid.

17/11/2022 22:06
Alert: freeChlorine is lower than normal (0.5)!
 Action:
 Check settings of chlorine pump and if necessary turn the automatic chlorine pump on.
 Add water.

Figure 4-7 DSS Feed for Carouge

DSS warnings are in a descend order, with the aim of ‘catching’ the last warning every time. As a result, the end-user can be aware of any unwanted situation and act accordingly.

Moreover, proposed actions are provided too, depending the generated alert.

- Last Operator Reports

Finally, the end-user is fully aware of knowledge and he/she can fill the “Daily Report” by clicking on its button.

- The end-user clicks on the “New Report” button.

Figure 4-8 New Report

When the end-user clicks, then the form below is opened:

The end-user can update the form with further details, such as observations, air temperature among others. These fields require text input and/or drop-down selection.

The end-user finishes and clicks on the “[Submit](#)” button.

Figure 4-9 Submit Button

Then, the end-user can see the daily form on the down-center, if he takes a glimpse at the “[Last Operator Reports](#)”.

Dernières observations

Température mesurée manuellement: 10

Animaux dans le bassin: 20

Chlore mesuré: 0.22

Chlore mesuré manuellement: 0

Date observation: 30/05/2022 15:19

Corps étrangers: 3

Lieu: fountainDesTours

Observation Kind: failure

Personnes: 5

pH mesuré: 7.13

pH (mesure manuelle): 0

Personnes dans le bassin: 0

Température: 19

Température eau: 21.3

Relevé compteur (manuel): 0

Température eau (mesure manuelle): 0

Figure 4-10 Last Operator Reports

This report receives the input of the Operator for the Daily Report and produces an overall picture of it. Moreover, this report demonstrates only the changed inputs every time it is submitted. In addition, HMI provides to the end-user the last 5 Operational reports, submitted by different users.

* The same functionalities are applied to Carouge Swimming pool, as the following figure shows.

Figure 4-11 Swimming Pool

In order to turn the Fountains to the Swimming Pool Screens, the end-user has to click on the drop-down on the top-left of the figure above.

Now, he can be aware of Swimming Pool too, by following the same path with the previous Fountain's navigation.

5. Water Observatory

The Water Observatory tool provided by JSI have the following functionalities. The current figures are not in French. JSI will provide them for HMI and for this document.

- **Indicators:** adding to the global indicators we are ingesting curated open datasets that have regional information about water topics of interest to the stakeholder.
- **Media:** each location has its own news and social media streams configured to priorities and aspects of the news that stakeholders define as topics of interest (e.g., floods).
- **Research:** similarly, to the media sources, the research topics allow for some customization to better fit to the needs of the local user.
- **Resources:** the natural resources information provided for exploration is geolocated to the regions of interest to the user of the platform.

5.1. Indicators View

To better understand the evolution and correlation between aspects impacting water resources, and to better observe alignment with Sustainable Development Goals, the NAIADES Water Observatory provides the user with a set of dropdown menus where the user can choose the data sources in a three-dimensional visualization. Here we consider a dynamic view over time on two axes and consider the size of balls to complete three dimensions of observation (see Figure below).

Figure 5.1-1 Multidimensional animation in the analysis of global indicators

The local priorities of the NAIADES use cases are addressed in the “Local Indicator” tab changing from data ingested from global to local indicators. This view is showcasing the observation of water-related datasets linked to SDG 6 at world and country/region levels that can help us observe changes and trends (see Figure below). Both the local and global indicators can ingest new data sources that are identified of interest to, e.g., new added users bringing new priorities.

Figure 5.1-2 Higher granularity in the analysis of local indicators

To complement the analysis of indicators that can be sometimes unclear when the user wants to follow the progress of a single indicator, we have made available a single-indicator view, both to analyse global and local indicators in separate, when scrolling down from the animation, maintaining the selections. It is also possible to view the time-series deriving from the countries selected at each of these indicators in a single window for in-depth analysis (see Figure below).

Figure 5.1-3 Analysis of a single indicator through time

An example of a workflow in the usage of this tab is to analyse the evolution of the water surface level, in comparison with the fresh surface water and the inland waters across 20 years in Spain, selecting the appropriate axis in the dropdown menu and changing the location from “All Countries” to “Spain”. The comparison with other countries is still visible but the behaviour for the case of Spain is highlighted. Then, to further analyse the “Alicante” case we select that case in the “Global” dropdown menu and have now available the “Local Indicators” tab. In this view, when focusing on the topic of the evolution of drinking water conditions in the past 20 years in Spain, we can compare, e.g., the volume of drinking water, to the apparent losses of drinking water and the aid to the volume of water supplied in the public network across Spanish regions.

5.2. Media View

Both the traditional news media and the social media are important sources of input to the analysis of best practices in similar scenarios, and the definition of early warnings for water events. This view is exploring the information from news and social media in the context of the exploration of water-related topics that include when the weather is favourable to floods and the historical information from news and published research on these weather-related events and how to better take decisions to solve them. The water-related news is sourced in real-time using powerful text mining methods based on Wikipedia concepts to collect about 1500 news articles per day across more than 60 languages, of which a part relates to water events around the world. When selecting the Use Case in the main menu on the left, the real-time stream of news is automatically configured to search for topics that relate to the priorities and interests of the stakeholders that helped define this view, thus addressing the local interests (see Figure below).

The screenshot displays the 'WATER OBSERVATORY - ALICANTE' web interface. At the top, there is a search bar with 'Query: Water contamination' and a country dropdown set to '-- All countries --'. There are also checkboxes for 'Reading mode' and 'Show English only', and a 'Paused' button. The main area features a map of Europe and Africa with a blue pin in Spain. A news alert box is overlaid on the map with the text: 'La Fundación Séneca convoca 23 contratos predoctorales de personal...' and 'Publisher: europa press'. To the right of the map, there is a news feed showing the same headline, the date 'Sun Jul 04 2021, 08:38', and a brief description: 'MURCIA, 4 Jul. (EUROPA PRESS) - La Fundación Séneca, dependiente de la Consejería de Empresa, Empleo, Universidades y Portavocía, ha convocado dos líneas de ayudas para apoyar el talento investigador, por importe de cerca de 900.000 euros. Se trata de 23 nuevos contratos predoctorales de formación del personal investigador y de 12 becas de formación posdoctoral en centros de investigación internacionales de referencia. [Read more](#)'. Below the map, there are logos for 'NAIADES', 'eventregistry', and 'Institut "Jožef Stefan" Ljubljana, Slovenija'. A legend at the bottom left of the map indicates 'Positive' (green), 'Neutral' (blue), and 'Negative' (red).

Figure 5.2-1 Water-related news monitoring

The configuration of the news streams is done directly over the news engine API that is serving them but can be tested in the news monitoring part of the system. The user can choose water topics of interest and define priority levels, choose languages and categories, as well as define how rigorous this configuration must be, to model how much news articles the system is collecting (see Figure below).

Figure 5.2-2 Comprehensive configuration of news sources

When the user aims to explore a certain water-related event, it can do so in the larger news engine EventRegistry. This will allow the user to further explore concepts related to the collected articles from a query, and the fundamental information that the news collection provides about the event. The user can explore the news through time and learn from what was published in the context of similar events in the region or other world regions where best practices can be derived and help planning for the future happenings (see Figure below).

Figure 5.2-3 Historical news analysis at the external exploration dashboard

The system also allows the user to explore other topics that are related to the query formulated over news articles or events, to better understand how much are other topics (e.g., economy or education) associated with the water topic in analysis. At all times the subsample of news articles can be requested for further analysis (see Figure below).

Figure 5.2-4 Water news categorification at the external exploration dashboard

The social media is also present through Facebook and Twitter with different data access characteristics, and applications. Through the news engine Event Registry, that we have access to in the context NAIADES supporting the research on the NWO, we are able to see the number of times that certain news is shared in Facebook and, thus, its impact in this online community.

On the other hand, we are also collecting the tweets related to certain water topics based on key-phrases in the original languages and locations of the NAIADES Use Cases. In the tab “Twitter Dashboard” we present several data visualisation modules and search boxes where the user can further configure the search to access, e.g., the average sentiment of the posts or the main topics over keywords (see Figure below).

Figure 5.2-5 Real-time analysis of Twitter data

Moreover, we are exploring the potential to extract real-time insights from social media based on the news story of a certain water-related event taking into consideration certain conditions from other data sources as, e.g., the weather. This interaction between news and social media is based on the ingestion of filtered news streams and on analytics on social media about weather-related events that can help decision-making and trigger alarms (see Figure below).

Figure 5.2-6 Analysis of Tweets and news articles over a certain water-related event

In line with the capabilities offered by this comprehensive view, one example of its usage can start by the real-time news monitoring of water-related events regarding the recent flooding in Germany and Belgium, to configure the social media collection to the weather conditions in order to provide specific alarms. Then, to use the news engine Event Registry to explore news related to this event and other similar in order to study the sequence of happenings and use this to better plan for this event in the location of the user of the Water Observatory.

Figure 5.2-7 Analysis of news and twitter posts over an exploration tool

Finally, the version 2 of the NWO also makes available an exploratory tool to review a certain water-related topic and explore its subtopics. As shown in Figure above, the NAIADES user can query using key phrases (under “”) and use connectives to refine the search. Moreover, the user can drag the target over the automatically generated colorful clusters of subtopics to reprioritize the search results according to the defined objectives of this activity. The typical usage is the query on a certain topic using connectors AND, OR and lucene-based language to search in the metadata. From the list of search results subtopics are generated and distributed into coloured clusters. The user will then drag the target over the subtopics that are more related to the aims of the study and with that movement the search results change position. The user can directly access the more relevant publications directly by clicking on their title.

5.3. Research View

The scientific research tab allows the user to explore the information provided by published science, and look in detail into the success stories that can be used in decision-making and water education at local level. While in the global view the user can compare the research on water topics across countries and years of publication (in the tab “top trends”), as well as the main trends on water-research and how they have changed along the past years. The user can change the scale to ease interpretation, or download the data and the chart itself (see Figure below).

Figure 5.3-1 Identification of trends in the scientific research

Figure 5.3-2 Analysis of scientific research using an exploration dashboard

The user can also access the most recent research papers directly at this “Research” view on the “Recent papers” tab, where the details of each paper is exposed. For a further analysis, the user can access the external dashboard based on the text mining technology Searchpoint that allows to explore the literature by moving the pointer over clusters of subtopics related to the query topic and, by doing that, to reorder the articles that were queried. At the moment this is limited to the research articles in the MEDLINE open dataset that mostly relate to health topics, being relevant to explore water contamination topics.

An example of usage of this view follows that of the exploration of historical news data to access further details on a water-related event. The user can start to analyse the trends related to such event and how they evolve through time (e.g., fresh water resources), and then explore those selected trends directly in the published literature by using them as key-phrases.

5.4. Resources View

In this second version we added the dimension of natural resources to the exploration scenarios of the Water Observatory, based on ingested weather data from the ECMWF (on humidity, temperature and rainfall) and other open data sources, with a sophisticated engine to explore the states of that data and short/medium term predictions on aspects of that data. This new view will explore topics related to water in the context of the climate crisis, offering in the tab “Predictions” the long-term predictions for over 5 to 10 years on, e.g., the behaviour of a season in what regards humidity, rainfall or water levels, based on the collected historical data (see Figure below).

Figure 5.4-1 Climate change visualization over 10 years forecast on resources availability

Moreover, it will also allow the user (through the tab “Explore”) to explore the data based on the Markov chains visual representation technology Streamstory that can show in an interactive way the distinctions between states and how they interact. This complex data visualisation model can provide additional information at each node and each transition that can help the user explore the combination of factors that explain the dynamics of, e.g., the season in regards to natural resources.

Figure 5.4-2 Exploration of water resources through complex data visualization

An example of usage of this view starts with the selection of topics that define the focus of the study (e.g., rainfall, humidity and water level) to analyse 5- and 10-years forecasts related to these. Then, the user will continue the analysis in the tab “Explore”, interacting with the data visualisation and exploring the relations between states, clicking on states and transitions to access their characteristics, and studying their impact in the context of the problem in analysis.

6. Conclusion

By following the above navigation approach, the end-user will be enhanced with situation awareness for the Fountain and the Swimming Pool area's anomalies. This knowledge will enable an accurate, real-time and worthy way of facing unwanted incidents, as water waste.

